

AMBASSADOR CLAVIJO TALKS ABOUT THE TRADITIONS OF HOSPITALITY DURING THE REIGN OF AMIR TEMUR

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Abstract. *The article studies the issues of the tradition of hospitality of Amir Temur, honored by the sovereign to guests led by the Spanish ambassador during a visit to Samarkand, based on the diary of Rui Gonzales de Glavijo.*

It is certainly not for nothing that Shavkat Mirziyoev claims that “Our grandfather Amir Temur, a great entrepreneur, emphasized in his will a very important thought that he left to us, the descendants, and said: “Your noble duty is to be a cure for hand pain”.

Keywords: *Sokhibkiran, Amir Timur, reign, Clavijo, hospitality, conventions, traditons, ceremonies, ambassadors, presents, foods, “Nine meals”.*

All peoples and nations of the world have hospitality customs and traditions, which are among the values that have been formed and polished for centuries. It is also recognized that these values and traditions are very similar and unique to each other in many nations. The Uzbek nation, which is considered to be a potential in the world, has its centuries-old traditions and customs of hospitality. It can be said that the tradition of hospitality in our people is shown at the level of value. There are certain "iron laws" of hospitality and welcoming guests, which are detailed in historical sources and in the heritage of our ancestors.

In the religion of Islam, it is established that every Muslim believer should respect his guest. Hospitality is given great importance in the Holy Quran and it is commanded to "Respect guests". It is said in the holy hadiths, "Whoever believes in God and the Last Day, should honor his guest." Rasulullah (s.a.v) said that "One night's feast for a guest is obligatory on every Muslim." Also, in the hadith, "A people who do not honor a guest are called an evil people." "There are proverbs in our people such as "The guest is a god", "The guest comes through the door, and the food comes through the hole".

In the Uzbek people, the traditions of hospitality are passed down from ancestors to generations, and the qualities of hospitality are instilled in the child from birth, in the family, environment, in the primary and upper grades of school, and later throughout his life. In ancient times, Uzbeks had inner and outer courtyards, and guests were welcomed in a special hotel located in the outer courtyard near the gate. In this case, 6-7-year-old boys were involved in welcoming the guests, which served as a kind of school. From a young age, the child has acquired important educational skills, such as welcoming guests, having a warm relationship with them, providing good service, and forming a culture of behavior in him.

The people of Turan have always been very hospitable, guests were welcomed with open faces, even if they didn't know the passenger, every opportunity was used to meet his needs. There are reports that if a traveler arrives in the village, the neighbor will argue with each other and compete with each other to entertain him, which also shows how generous, open-handed and hospitable the local people are.

Being one of the most fertile, flourishing and bountiful regions of the world, the fruits of Turonzamin are more abundant and sweeter than those of other countries. People often ate more

meat from horses. The guests were treated with delicacies grown in our country and were treated with respect.

In many sources and works dedicated to the study of the reign of the Great Amir Temur, his life path, childhood and adolescence, his family, children, grandchildren, the kingdom he ruled, his creativity and beautification works, his patronage of the people of science, his attention to the development of culture and art, state administration system, there is information about his achievements in the political and military spheres.

However, the hospitality qualities of His Holiness, the traditions of hospitality in his kingdom have been left behind by researchers. In our opinion, hospitality of the great ruler, along with other high human virtues, arouses great interest in everyone. After all, these noble values also help to study the lifestyle and customs of our ancestors in depth.

There are some information about the hospitality qualities of Amir Temur in the form of records in the form of diaries and memoirs of a few persons who were guests in his presence or ambassadors and travelers who visited the territory of the country.

There is information in the works and diaries written by such historians as Nizamiddin Shami², Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi³, Ibn Arabshah⁴, and Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo⁵, dedicated to studying the life and activities of the owner. Among such rare sources, the "Diary" of Spanish (Castile) ambassador Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, who was in the Temurbek palace in Samarkand in the fall of 1404, is one of the most important sources.

In this "Diary" it is explained that when Amir Temur's officials returned from military campaigns in Iran and Khurasan, they brought homeless, poor citizens, orphans and the poor along with them to Samarkand, and according to the instructions of the great ruler, they were provided with all the necessary things.

On August 21, 1404, the ambassadors led by Claviho arrived in the city of Termiz, which was very large and populated, although the city was not surrounded by walls and fences, but surrounded by gardens and canals. Travelers are treated with respect in this city, provided with clothing and all other necessities.

According to the "Diary" of the ambassador, there is information that the servants of Amir Temur met with the ambassadors, always informed about their condition and gave horses as gifts to the guests. "Diary" also contains information about the owner's hospitality, hospitality, and the gifts he gave to guests.

In his "Diary" Clavijo said that he was in the city of Kesh on Thursday, August 28, that it was a large city, surrounded by a protective wall and deep ditches, it was located on a flat ground, irrigation canals and rivers ran through the city from all sides, it was prosperous, the suburban population dwells on the fact that it is surrounded by residences and gardens. He also noted that wheat, grapes, cotton, melons and other various fruits and vegetables were grown in the irrigated fields, and noted that guests who came to this area were treated with fruits.

Another of the information written down by the ambassador about Amir Temur's hospitality, it was reported that his father and son Jahangir were buried in Shahrisabz, and in these places twenty cooked sheep were sacrificed to the poor every day in memory of the father and son, and a party was organized in honor of the guests in this place, and a lot of meat was eaten. and it is recorded that they entertained the guests with fruits and took them to the big palace to spend the night. It was also noted that on Saturday, August 30, the guests dined and rested in a large house in a large, beautiful garden belonging to Amir Temur.

Finally, on Thursday, August 11, when Ambassador Klaviho and his companions arrived in the city of Samarkand, they were allowed to place them in a garden called Gulbog and pitch a tent. He skillfully described that the garden where the ambassador and his companions settled was very beautiful and beautiful. Also, information was recorded in the "Diary" that the guests were given a large amount of meat products and provided with other necessary things.

On Thursday, September 4, 1404, the owner sent his men to the garden where the foreign guests were staying and told them that he could not meet them yet, so that they would not get bored, he organized a celebration in their honor on the same day. They brought a lot of sheep to the guests and prepared a lot of food. Rice was cooked in different ways, horse meat was roasted and various fruits were served to the guests. At the end of the event, the guests were given two horses, hats and other clothes, and gifts.

There is information that Temurbek welcomed foreign guests not inside the city of Samarkand, but in magnificent gardens outside the city and entertained them in these gardens. During the Timur's period, there were a lot of such gardens, and they were created very luxuriously.

Full information about Amir Temur's hospitality qualities was shown in his several meetings with Spanish ambassadors. In particular, Sohigiron expressed his desire to see the guests on Monday, September 8, and received them in Bogi Dilkusho. The guests were told to hand over the gifts they had brought to the great ruler to the servants. The servants tried to present the gifts to Temurbek in a beautiful way. They brought the gifts to the court of the ruler, and the guests paid respect by kneeling with their right feet and crossing their hands on their chests.

Temurbek asked them to come closer. After that, seeing that the ambassadors were sitting lower than the Chinese ambassadors, he showed them a special favor by asking them to sit lower, and the Spanish ambassadors closer to him, i.e. higher. In all subsequent official meetings and receptions, this arrangement was maintained, and the guests were placed in this order.

One of the distinctive aspects of the hospitality of the Sahibqiran period was that the more distant and respectable the guest was, the longer the guest was received. For example, Chinese ambassadors came to Samarkand in 1395, but they met with the great ruler only in 1397. Also, the gifts brought by the guests were kept for a certain period, and only then were they presented to the Host.

Clavijo's "Diary" contains the following points about hospitality: the guests were seated in a fixed order, they were treated to a large amount of cooked, fried and salted mutton and horse meat. Gold, silver and ceramic dishes were used for hospitality. The so-called porcelain vessel was considered very valuable and valuable. The ambassadors were given a leg of horse meat intact, whole but with the bones removed. Out of respect for them, Amir Temur weighed the food in two dishes placed in front of him, the meat products placed in front of the guests were immediately collected and sent home. Failure to perform this duty is considered disrespectful. There were so many meat products in the round that even its amount reached up to six months.

The fact that meat products were served as the next meal during hospitality shows that meat products were consumed a lot in those times. After the main meals, many fruits, including melons, grapes, and apricots, were placed on the table, and gold and silver jugs were served.

At the end of the hospitality ceremony, servants were attached to Clavijo to take care of the guests, and they were placed in a separate building in the garden not far from the house where the great ruler lived, and special respect was shown.

On September 15, the next reception was held, and the main purpose of this gathering was to introduce the guests to the relatives of Amir Temur. Since there was no interpreter among those who went to invite the guests, they arrived late. By the time they visited, the great ruler had already finished his meal. Therefore, Amir Temur sent five sheep and two large jugs of wine to the house where the guests were staying.

In "Diary" the meeting with the Spanish ambassadors in Dilkusho Garden of Sahibqiran and the great respect shown to them, the traditions of hospitality, cooking skills, dishes decorated with precious stones, tents, buildings, and structures built on the level of architectural masterpieces, and the interior and exterior of the building are covered. At the end of the party, guests were showered with silver coins, gold accessories, and precious stones. In order to show respect to the guests who came from afar, and to improve their economic situation, ambassador Clavijo and his companions were several times weighed with silver coins, and silver coins were sprinkled on their heads. This situation can be seen as a unique development of the hospitality industry during the period of Amir Temur.

In the next hospitality, Amir Temur's elder wife Bibikhanim (Saraymulkkhanum) personally showed her respect for the ambassadors led by Klavijo. This shows that during the time when Sahibkiran lived, the traditions of hospitality in our nation were instilled in every family member and citizen.

There is also information about the number of gifts given to Amir Temur in the "Diary" that was nine, and even today, when the groom comes to take the bride out of her house, nine types of food are placed in front of her - "nine plates", and the number of clothing cloths that are put in the bride's dowry is nine. that it is called "nine plates" shows that it is a continuation of traditions that have been going on for a long time in our nation.

It is also noted in "Diary" that entertainment events were organized at parties organized in honor of the guests. Musicians participated in such ceremonies, performances were performed with decorated elephants, and hanging competitions were organized.

The amount of meat on the table was so large that more than 300 people were involved to serve it to the guests. The meat was dragged round the floor in a gold-plated leather dish, and according to custom, the servants divided it among the dishes and then passed it to the guests. During the entire hospitality period, horse and mutton meat, prepared in various ways, was constantly transported in special containers on carts and camels and delivered to the guests one after the other.

On Friday, November 21, Ambassador Klavikho's mission completed the work they had planned in Samarkand and returned to their homeland. Observers were attached to them along the way. Clavijo's group arrived in Bukhara on Thursday, November 27, and were greeted with gifts during their seven-day stay. They left Bukhara on December 5, crossed the Amudarya River on December 10 and left the border. In the country of Amir Temur, they were given a special document - a label stating that they should be provided with horses, food, clothing and other most necessary things by the officials assigned to each region, and the guests were treated with respect, which is also the hospitality virtue of the great host and the guests. clearly shows his relatively high respect.

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